

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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METHODOLOGY FOR PLACING TYPES OF GREEN BONDS

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Abstract: This article determines the novelty of this type of attracting financing to the economy, the increase in the number and volume of green bond +issues in developed and developing countries due to global greening trends, as well as government support provided to environmentally friendly projects and used in their financing through securities. A number of specific requirements are imposed on the issue of "green" bonds, for example, verification, which is carried out before such securities are allowed to be placed on the market and is an independent environmental assessment of the project by a third party.

Key words: green bonds, bond proceeds, project bonds, insured bonds, green bond placement mechanism, environmental projects.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola iqtisodiyotga moliyalashtirishni jalb qilishning ushbu turining yangiligi, rivojlangan va rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlarda global yashillashtirish tendentsiyalari tufayli yashil obligatsiyalar + emissiyalari soni va hajmining ko'payishi, shuningdek, ekologik toza loyihalarni davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlash va ularni qimmatli qog'ozlar orqali moliyalashtirishda foydalanilishini belgilaydi. "Yashil" obligatsiyalar chiqarishga bir qator aniq talablar qo'yiladi, masalan, bunday qimmatli qog'ozlarni bozorga chiqarishga ruxsat berilgunga qadar amalga oshiriladigan va uchinchi shaxs tomonidan loyihaning mustaqil ekologik bahosi bo'lgan tekshirish.

Kalit so'zlar: yashil obligatsiyalar, obligatsiya tushumlari, loyiha obligatsiyalari, sug'urtalangan obligatsiyalar, yashil obligatsiyalarni joylashtirish mexanizmi, ekologik loyihalar.

Аннотация: В данной статье определяется новизна данного вида привлечения финансирования в экономику, увеличение количества и объемов выпусков зеленых облигаций в развитых и развивающихся странах в связи с глобальными тенденциями экологизации, а также государственной поддержки, оказываемой экологически чистым проектам и используемой при их финансировании за счет ценных бумаг. К выпуску «зеленых» облигаций предъявляется ряд специфических требований, например, проверка, которая проводится перед размещением таких ценных бумаг на рынке и представляет собой независимую экологическую оценку проекта третьей стороной.

Ключевые слова: зеленые облигации, доход от облигаций, проектные облигации, застрахованные облигации, механизм размещения зеленых облигаций, экологические проекты.

INTRODUCTION

Green bonds are debt securities that are issued to attract investment in projects aimed at improving the environmental situation or at least minimizing harm to nature.

Green bonds were created to finance projects that have positive environmental and climate benefits. Most green bonds issued are of the following types:

- "green" bonds "use of proceeds";
- "green" bonds linked to assets;
- "green" project bonds;
- "green securitized" bonds.

The proceeds from these bonds are earmarked for green projects but are secured by the entire balance sheet of the issuer.

LITERATURE REVIEW OF THE TOPIC

The term “green bonds” emerged relatively recently as a new instrument for financing the economy. According to economists such as T. Ehlers and F. Packer [5], these securities offer a premium yield compared to traditional bonds, while their liquidity and efficiency in the secondary market remain at a similar level.

J. Banga [6] views the growth of the green bond market as a natural phenomenon in both developed and developing countries, largely driven by the transparency of issuances. At the same time, P. Deshriver and F. Maris [7] express skepticism about these instruments, pointing to several obstacles: the lack of globally agreed standards, high issuance costs, and a limited supply of such securities for investors.

Among domestic studies, the work of M. Karimov [4] is noteworthy. In his economic review, he analyzes various types of green bonds and emphasizes that this instrument facilitates the attraction of additional financing for enterprises without state participation while also increasing the profitability of environmentally oriented projects.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Green bonds have some additional transaction costs as issuers must track, monitor and report the use of proceeds. However, many issuers, especially repeat issuers of green bonds, offset these initial costs with the following benefits:

- Highlights its green assets or business;
- Positive marketing history.

Proceeds from the issuance of bonds are used to implement green projects, which must be properly described in the documentation for the issue of securities. All specified green projects must bring environmental benefits, subject to assessment by the issuer in terms of qualitative and, if possible, quantitative characteristics.

The Green Bond Principles explicitly provide for several broad categories of eligible green projects that contribute to environmental goals, such as climate change mitigation, climate change adaptation, natural resource conservation, biodiversity conservation, and pollution prevention and control.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

According to the placement method, green bonds are of the following types:

- Direct issue bonds;
- Securitized bonds. Before their release, collateral assets are aggregated, which in the future are the guarantor of payments on the bonds (fig.1).

Fig 1. Diagram of subtypes of green bonds.

Source: The diagram was prepared by the author using economic literature

Subtypes of direct issue bonds:

Government or municipal and general obligation bonds issued by international banks and financial institutions. This type of placement provides for the usual payments on obligations for this type of bonds;

General obligation corporate bonds. Such bonds are issued to finance their own green projects. Corporations guarantee the payment of bonds with their balance sheet;

Project bonds. Payments are guaranteed by the cash flow of the infrastructure project, as well as by banks and subnational authorities, if they provide such guarantees;

Income bonds. Payments are made through the sale of goods and services produced as a result of the project (fig.2).

Fig 2. Subtypes of securitized green bonds.

Source: The diagram was prepared by the author using economic literature

Insured green bonds differ from each other in the method of payment, for example, some green bonds are paid from the active part of the issuer's balance sheet, the so-called covered bonds, while others are guaranteed by the future earnings of the eco project, such bonds are called covered bonds, while others are secured by a pool of assets.

The approach taken in this methodology aims to demonstrate the ambitions of green bond issuers. Bonds are placed according to the following algorithm:

Step 1: Definition of labeled social and sustainable development debt;

Step 2: Using Revenue Analysis;

Step 3: Key information and mapping of sustainable development goals.

The green bond market is experiencing exponential growth. It reached its most significant peak: cumulative bond issuance since the market's inception in 2007 amounted to US\$1 trillion. This milestone was passed at the beginning of December 2020.

In the 13 years since the market's inception, it has been estimated that the average annual growth rate is approximately 95% (fig.3).

Fig.3 Growth dynamics of the green bond market.

Source: The diagram was prepared by the author using economic literature

The very first green bonds were issued in 2007 with a AAA rating by the multilateral institutions of the European Investment Bank (EIB) and the World Bank. The market took off in 2014 and has closed at record highs every year since.

The broader bond market began to respond after IFC issued its first green bond in March 2013, worth US\$1 billion, which was sold within an hour of IFC's release.

An encouraging feature of the green finance market has been the significant growth in green debt instruments, including green loans and sukuk. Green instruments have emerged in a record sixty-seven countries and multiple supranational institutions (table 1).

Table 1. Types of Green Bonds.

Types of Green Bonds	Income received from the sale of bonds	Debt reversal	Examples
Bond "Use of Proceeds"	Designed for green projects	Issuer Notice: The same credit rating as the issuer's other bonds applies	Climate Awareness Bond (supported by the EIB); Barclays Green Bonds
Revenue Obligation «Use of Proceeds» or ABS	Designated for green projects or refinanced	Revenue streams from issuers although fees, taxes, etc. are collateral for debt	State of Hawaii (provided by state utility electric commission)
Project bonds	Limited to specific basic green projects	Recourse is possible only in relation to the assets and balance of the project	Invenergy Wind Farm (supported by Invenergy Campo Palomas Wind Farm)
Securitization (ABS)	Bonds Refinancing of green project portfolios or proceeds from them can be used for green projects	The appeal is to a group of projects that have been grouped together (for example, a solar lease or a green mortgage)	Tesla Energy (supported by residential solar leases); Obvion (supported by green mortgages)
Cover Bonds	Intended for eligible projects included in the indoor pool	Recourse to the issuer and, if the issuer is unable to repay the bond, to the covered pool Berlin Hyp green Pfandbrief	Green secured bond Sparebank 1 Bolligkredit
Loan	Intended for eligible projects or backed by eligible assets	Full recourse to the borrower(s) in case of unsecured loans. Recourse to collateral in the case of secured loans, but may also provide limited recourse to the borrower(s)	MEP Werke, Ivanhoe Cambridge and Natixis Assurances (DUO), OVG
Other debt instruments	intended for eligible projects		Convertible bonds or notes, Schuldschein, commercial paper, sukuk, debentures

Source: The diagram was prepared by the author using economic literature

Modern investors, especially international ones, are becoming more socially responsible and take environmental and social factors into account when making investment decisions. So, if in 2017 only 8% of international investors paid attention to these factors in connection with the impact of the state of the environment on climate change, then in 2018 - 48%.

This explosive growth in interest in environmental issues is reflected in the international green bond market, although their yield is lower than that of ordinary bonds, but thanks to them, firstly, the image of companies improves, and secondly, they receive tax benefits, and - third, the company is exposed to fewer investment risks.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Our country is also taking a number of measures to improve the infrastructure for the circulation of green bonds. It should be noted that Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers dated July 20, 2023 No. 300 “On measures aimed at improving the environmental situation in certain industries, reducing the negative impact of waste on the environment and public health, and the effective use of alternative energy sources” [1].

Due to the adoption of this legislative act, there has been active growth in areas such as the construction industry, metallurgy, chemical and textile industries. It should be noted that our country is actively and quite successfully pursuing a policy of issuing Eurobonds, which indicates that the issuance of green bonds will also progress, and the infrastructure will be improved under the influence of the current economic situation.

List of used literature

1. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 300 dated 20.07.2023 “On measures aimed at improving the environmental situation in certain industrial sectors, reducing the negative impact of waste on the environment and public health, and the efficient use of alternative energy sources.”
2. Semenova N. N. “Green Economy”: New Approaches to Financing. *Financial Life*. 2019;(2):30–35.
3. Banga J. The Green Bond Market: A Potential Source of Climate Finance for Developing Countries. *Journal of Sustainable Finance and Investment*. 2019;9(1):17–32.
4. https://www.climatebonds.net/files/reports/cbi_gbm_final_032019_web.pdf.
5. Ehlers T, Packer F. Green Bond Finance and Certification. *BIS Quarterly Review*, September 2017.
6. Banga J. The Green Bond Market: A Potential Source of Climate Finance for Developing Countries. *Journal of Sustainable Finance and Investment*. 2019.
7. Deschryver P, Mariz de F. What Future for the Green Bond Market? How Can Policymakers, Companies, and Investors Unlock the Potential of the Green Bond Market? *Risk Financial Management*, 2020.
8. Analytical Report “Assessment of Development Financing for the Republic of Uzbekistan” as part of the implementation of a joint project of the United Nations Development Programme and the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan. UNDP, 2021.

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